

Analogy between the Syntheses of Indolizines and Phosphaindolizines[†]

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In 1991 we reported for the first time the synthesis of the phosphorus analogue of indolizine, namely, 1,3-azaphospholo[1,5-*a*]pyridine and named it as 2-phosphaindolizine¹. The synthetic strategy for this new organophosphorus heterocyclic system was analogous to the Kröhnke's synthesis of pyrrolo[1,5-*a*]pyridine, i.e. indolizine involving [4+1]cyclocondensation of 1,2-dialkylpyridinium salt with a carboxylic acid derivative². This was followed by the extension of another synthetic method of indolizines³⁻⁵, namely, [3+2]cycloaddition to phosphaindolizines⁶. We later found that [4+1]cyclocondensation method could be conveniently extended to the phosphorus analogues of azaindolizines and diazaindolizines also⁷⁻⁹. In fact subsequent work in our own group clearly indicated that a close analogy exists between the synthetic methods of indolizines and their phosphorus analogues¹⁰ and in near future the hitherto unknown phosphaindolizines might become accessible through the modified synthetic methods applicable to the indolizines and azaindolizines.

In the present review an attempt has been made to highlight analogies between the syntheses of two heterocyclic systems.

Synthetic strategies

Synthetic methods generally used for indolizines can be classified into four groups : (A) [4+1]cyclocondensation, (B) [3+2]cyclocondensation, (C) [3+2]cycloaddition and (D) 1,5-electrocyclization. Syntheses of indolizine along with its aza- and phospho-analogues are described here in the same

order.

Structures of different indolizines and phosphaindolizines along with the method used for their syntheses are given above.

[4+1]Cyclocondensation

In this approach annulated five-membered heterocyclic ring is constructed through condensation of a four-atom fragment with a reagent furnishing =CR- or =P- moiety. A carboxylic acid derivative supplies a carbon atom whereas PCl_3 or $\text{P}(\text{NMe}_2)_3$ is used for providing a phosphorus atom^{11,12} for this purpose.

Synthesis of indolizines :

1,2-Dialkylpyridinium salts (1) condense with acid anhydride in the presence of sodium acetate to give indolizines^{2,3,13-15} (2) (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

Synthesis of 2-phosphaindolizines :

1,2-Dialkylpyridinium bromides (1) condense likewise with PCl_3 in the presence of Et_3N to give 2-phosphaindolizines (4) (Scheme 2) in good yields^{1,16,17}. A good number of representatives having varying substituents could be prepared by this method.

Scheme 2

Sufficient activation of the *N*-methylene group is prerequisite for the above condensation, in the absence of which the reaction may stop at the intermediate stage. Furthermore, the reaction proceeds through the intermediacy of *N*-pyridiniumdichlorophosphinomethylide¹ (3). If the *N*-methylene group is not sufficiently activated, the reaction is instead initiated at 2-methyl group and 1-dichlorophosphino-2-phosphaindolizine (6) is formed through the intermediacy

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648

of 1-alkyl-2-{bis(dichlorophosphino)methylene}-1,2-dihydropyridine¹⁸ (**5**) (Scheme 3).

Scheme 3

The above cyclocondensation method has been found to be quite versatile and has been extended to the syntheses of 1,3-azaphospholo[1,5-*a*]pyrazines¹, 1,3-azaphospholo[5,1-*b*]thiazolines¹⁹, 1,3-azaphospholo[5,1-*b*]benzothiazoles¹⁹ and 1,3-azaphospholo[5,1-*b*]oxazolines²⁰.

Synthesis of 1-phosphaindolizines :

1,3-Oxazolo[3,2-*a*]pyridinium salts (**7**) incorporate a four-membered chain and condense with $\text{P}(\text{SiMe}_3)_3$ to give 1-phosphaindolizines (**8**) through O/P exchange²¹ (Scheme 4).

Scheme 4

Synthesis of 1-azaindolizines :

Imidazo[1,2-*a*]pyridines, i.e. 1-azaindolizines (**10**) have been prepared from the condensation of 2-amino-1-benzylpyridinium bromides (**9**) with acetic anhydride²² (Scheme 5).

Scheme 5

Synthesis of 1-aza-2-phosphaindolizines :

We obtained 1,4,2-diazaphospholo[4,5-*a*]pyridines, i.e. 1-aza-2-phosphaindolizines (**13**) by condensing 1-alkyl-2-aminopyridinium salts (**11**) with PCl_3 in the presence of Et_3N ⁷ (Scheme 6).

Scheme 6

In this case, the reaction is initiated at 2-amino group and the intermediate (1-alkyl-2-pyridinylideneamino)-dichlorophosphine (**12**) could be isolated by carrying out the reaction in a nonpolar solvent like benzene or toluene. In the case of $\text{R}^1 = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$ or *p*-Me- C_6H_4 , **12** does not change into the corresponding 1-aza-2-phosphaindolizine even on prolonged heating in the presence of excess Et_3N .

This method has been extended to some other annulated diazaphospholes, namely, 1,4,2-diazaphospholo[4,5-*a*]thiazoles^{23,24}, -thiazolines²³ and -benzothiazoles²³.

Synthesis of 3-azaindolizines :

Pyrazolo[1,5-*a*]pyridines, i.e. 3-azaindolizines (**15**) have been prepared from the condensation of 2-alkyl-1-aminopyridinium halides (**14**) with acid anhydride or acyl chloride^{25,26} (Scheme 7).

Scheme 7

Benzaldehyde has also been used in place of acid derivative to obtain 3-azaindolizine²⁷.

Synthesis of 3-aza-2-phosphaindolizines :

Analogously, we prepared 1,2,3-diazaphospholo[1,5-*a*]pyridines, i.e. 3-aza-2-phosphaindolizines (**16**) from the condensation of 2-alkyl-1-aminopyridinium iodides (**14**) with PCl_3 in the presence of Et_3N ⁸ (Scheme 8).

Scheme 8

Synthesis of 3-aza-1-phosphaindolizines :

Like 1-phosphaindolizines, 1,2,4-diazaphospholo[1,5-*a*]pyridines, i.e. 3-aza-1-phosphaindolizines (**18**) have been prepared through O/P exchange of 1,3,4-oxadiazolo[3,2-*a*]pyridinium salts (**17**) with $\text{P}(\text{SiMe}_3)_3$ ^{21,28} (Scheme 9).

Scheme 9

Synthesis of 1,3-diazaindolizines :

1,2-Diaminopyridinium iodides (**19**) or pregenerated 1-amino-2-imino-2*H*-pyridine (**20**) condense with acid chloride or acid anhydride to give 1,2,4-triazolo[1,5-*a*]pyridines, i.e. 1,3-diazaindolizines^{29,30} (**21**) (Scheme 10).

Scheme 10

Synthesis of 1,3-diaza-2-phosphaindolizines :

Likewise, we obtained 1,2,4,3-triazaphospholo[1,5-*a*]pyridines, i.e. 1,3-diaza-2-phosphaindolizines (22) from cyclocondensation of 1,2-diaminopyridinium iodides (19) with $\text{P}(\text{NMe}_2)_3$ in refluxing benzene⁹ (Scheme 11).

Scheme 11

On using PCl_3 in place of $\text{P}(\text{NMe}_2)_3$, either the product is not formed at all or the yield is very poor. Two representatives of 22 have been obtained from the reaction of 1-amino-2-imino-2*H*-pyridine (20) with $\text{P}(\text{NMe}_2)_3$ ³¹.

[3+2]Cyclocondensation

In this approach, the annulated pyrrole ring of indolizine is constructed from the condensation of a three-atom fragment present in 2-alkylpyridine or 2-aminopyridine with two-atom fragment, α -halocarbonyl compound in the presence of a base³². Karaghiosoff *et al.* made use of chloromethyl-dichlorophosphine³³ ($\text{ClCH}_2\text{PCl}_2$) as an equivalent reagent furnishing two-membered C-P moiety for cyclocondensation with 2-substituted azoles and azines³⁴.

Synthesis of indolizines :

A variety of indolizines (25) has been obtained from [3+2]cyclocondensation of 2-alkylpyridine (23) with α -haloketone³⁵ (24) (Scheme 12). Unsubstituted indolizine has been prepared from the condensation of 2-methylpyridine with bromoacetaldehyde³⁵.

Scheme 12

In place of 2-alkylpyridine, ethylpyridine-2-carboxylate has also been used³⁶. Similarly, differently substituted α -halocarbonyl compounds have been used to obtain differently substituted indolizines³⁶⁻³⁸. An attempted analogous synthesis of phosphaindolizines from the condensation of 2-alkylpyridine with $\text{ClCH}_2\text{PCl}_2$ in the presence of Et_3N failed³⁹.

Synthesis of 1-azaindolizines :

The imidazo[1,2-*a*]pyridine, i.e. 1-azaindolizine (27) was first prepared from the reaction of bromoacetaldehyde with 2-aminopyridine⁴⁰ (26) (Scheme 13).

Scheme 13

In place of α -bromoacetaldehyde, α,β -unsaturated ketone has also been used in the above synthesis⁴¹.

Synthesis of 1-aza-2-phosphaindolizines :

2-Aminopyridine (26) condenses with $\text{ClCH}_2\text{PCl}_2$ in the presence of Et_3N to give 1,4,2-diazaphospholo[4,5-*a*]pyridine, i.e. 1-aza-2-phosphaindolizine (28) regioselectively^{34,42,43}. Preferential attack of stronger electrophilic phosphorus of $\text{ClCH}_2\text{PCl}_2$ on more nucleophilic 2-amino group of 2-aminopyridine is probably responsible for regioselectivity (Scheme 14).

Scheme 14

The above synthetic method could be successfully employed for several other annulated diazaphospholes^{34,42}.

[3+2]Cycloaddition

N-Pyridinium and other cycloiminium ylides and imines act as 1,3-dipoles and undergo [3+2]cycloaddition with acetylenic or olefinic 1,3-dipolarophiles to give indolizine derivatives⁴⁴⁻⁴⁶.

Synthesis of indolizines :

A variety of acetylenic 1,3-dipolarophiles (30) like dimethyl acetylenedicarboxylate (DMAD), cyanoacetylene, phenylcyanoacetylene has been used which on [3+2]cycloaddition with *N*-pyridinium ylides (29) followed by 1,4-elimination give differently substituted indolizines⁴⁷⁻⁴⁹ (32) (Scheme 15).

Regioselectivity of the reaction is determined by the nature of the substituent group present in pyridinium ylide and dipolarophile^{50,51}. Likewise, olefinic 1,3-dipolarophiles (31) like methyl acrylate⁵²⁻⁵⁴ or maleic anhydride⁴⁸ have

Scheme 15

also been used. In one case, ethyl acetoacetate has been used as 1,3-dipolarophile⁵⁵.

Synthesis of 1-phospha- and 2-phosphaindolizines :

Regitz and coworkers have used *tert*-butylphosphaacetylene as 1,3-dipolarophile⁵⁶⁻⁵⁹ which condenses with pyridinium ylide (29) to give 2-phosphaindolizine (33) regiospecifically⁶ (Scheme 16).

Scheme 16

The reactions of pyridinium (34, X = CH, Y = CH), pyridazinium (34, X = N, Y = CH) and pyrazinium (34, X = CH, Y = N) dicyanomethylides with *tert*-butylphosphaacetylene are however not regiospecific and a mixture of the isomeric heterocycles 35 and 36 is formed in each case⁶. Regioselectivity is again observed on introducing a *tert*-butyl or isopropoxy group in the 4-position of 34 (X = CH, Y = CH)⁶ (Scheme 17).

Scheme 17

The above synthetic method has been extended to isoquinolinium and phthalazinium ylides to give the corresponding annulated azaphospholes⁶. Azaphosphauillazines have also been prepared through this route⁶⁰.

Synthesis of 3-azaindolizines :

N-Pyridinium imines (37) formed by the action of potassium carbonate on *N*-aminopyridinium iodides undergo [3+2]cycloaddition with alkyl propynoate to form 3-azaindolizines⁶¹⁻⁶³ (38) (Scheme 18).

Likewise, some other 1,3-dipolarophiles, namely, DMAD⁶⁴, cyanoacetylene⁵⁰, ethyl acetoacetate⁶⁵, ethyl β -chloroisocrotonate⁶⁵ or ketenethioacetals⁶⁶⁻⁶⁸ have also

Scheme 18

been used in the above reaction.

No report has so far appeared for the synthesis of 3-aza-2-phospha- or 3-aza-1-phosphaindolizine through this synthetic route. It may however be expected that *N*-pyridinium imines might undergo [3+2]cycloaddition with phosphoacetylene to give 3-azaphosphaindolizines.

1,5-Electrocyclization

An unsaturated system having 1,3-dipolar moiety bonded directly to an olefinic or acetylenic bond possesses 1,5-dipolar structure as one of the contributing forms and undergoes 1,5-electrocyclization to form a five-membered heterocyclic ring (Scheme 19). Huisgen⁶⁹ proved it to be a symmetry-allowed electrocyclic ring closure.

Scheme 19

Azomethine ylides and azomethine imines incorporate such structure and have been utilized for the synthesis of five-membered heterocycles⁷⁰.

Synthesis of indolizines :

The pyridinium *N*-allylides generated by deprotonation of the *N*-pyridinium salts act as potential 1,5-dipoles and undergo intramolecular 1,5-electrocyclization followed by dehydrogenation to give indolizines⁷¹⁻⁷⁸. Tamura *et al.*⁷¹ obtained indolizines (41) through their dihydro derivatives (40) which are formed on deprotonation of the pyridinium salts (39). The latter were generated from the reaction of the pyridine with 4-bromo-1,3-biphenyl-2-butene-1-one (Scheme 20).

Scheme 20

In another approach, *N*-allylpyridinium ylides were generated *in situ* by the reaction of *N*-pyridinium ylides with methoxyethylene compounds which on 1,5-electrocyclization afforded indolizines⁷⁹.

Synthesis of 2-phosphaindolizines :

Recently we reported the synthesis of *N*-pyridiniumdichlorophosphinomethylides from the reaction of PCl_3 with *N*-alkylpyridinium bromides in presence of Et_3N ¹⁸. Schmidpeter *et al.* observed that dichlorophosphino-methylenetriphenylphosphonium ylides (42) underwent disproportionation to generate the species 43^{80,81} (Scheme 21).

Scheme 21

Disproportionation of the corresponding *N*-pyridiniumdichlorophosphinomethylides (44) would generate the species bis(*N*-pyridiniumylidyl)phosphenium chloride (45) which being a 1,5-dipole would undergo 1,5-electrocyclization (Scheme 22). In fact on leaving a solution of 44 in methylene chloride, 2-phosphaindolizine (46) is obtained which is formed through successive disproportionation and 1,5-electrocyclization followed by loss of the pyridinium hydrochloride⁸².

Scheme 22

Alternatively, 45 can be generated by the reaction of *N*-pyridiniumdichlorophosphinomethylides (44) with the *N*-pyridinium ylides (47) (Scheme 22). In the one-pot synthesis, 46 could be prepared from the reaction of 48 with PCl_3 (1/2 equiv.) in the presence of Et_3N (2 equiv.) in a polar solvent like methylene chloride (Scheme 23).

Scheme 23

On carrying out a crossed reaction between 49 and 50, all the four possible isomers 51, 52, 53 and 54 are formed⁸² (Scheme 24).

Synthesis of 3-azaindolizines :

Like pyridinium *N*-allylides, *N*-vinyliminopyridinium ylides also incorporate a 1,5-dipolar system and can lead to azaindolizine⁷⁰. Sasaki *et al.*⁸³ generated *N*-vinylimino-

Scheme 24

pyridinium ylides (57) from the reaction of *N*-aminopyridinium iodides (55) with dimethyl 1-chlorofumarate (56) or -maleate which subsequently cyclized and aromatized by dehydrogenation to give 3-azaindolizines (58) (Scheme 25). Methyl 3-bromomethaacrylate⁸⁴ or 3,3-bis(methylthio)-1-nitroethylene⁸⁵ have also been used in place of 56.

Scheme 25

Reaction of *N*-aminopyridinium iodide (55) with PCl_3 and Et_3N in benzene generates *N*-pyridiniumdichlorophosphinoimine (59) ($\delta^{31}\text{P} = 110$ ppm). The latter however does not undergo subsequent disproportionation and 1,5-electrocyclization⁸⁶ (Scheme 26).

Scheme 26

Synthesis of 1,3-diazaindolizines :

The strategy of using *N*-iminopyridinium ylide as precursor has been extended to the synthesis of 1,3-diazaindolizines also⁸⁷. *N*-Imidoiminopyridinium ylides (60) on thermal cyclization afforded 1,3-diazaindolizine (61) and 3-azaindolizine (62) in different ratios depending upon the substituents in the pyridinic ring⁸⁷ (Scheme 27).

Scheme 27

Synthesis of 1,2-diazaindolizines :

1,2-Diazaindolizines (**65**) have been prepared through 1,5-electrocyclization of 2-pyridylnitrilimine (**64**) generated *in situ* from benzylidene 2-pyridylhydrazone⁸⁸ (**63**) (Scheme 28).

Scheme 28

2-Pyridylnitrilimine could be generated from 2-hydrazidopyridines also by the action of thionyl chloride followed by elimination of SO₂⁸⁹.

Synthesis of 2,3-diazaindolizines :

2,3-Diazaindolizine (**68**) has been prepared from 1,5-electrocyclization of the intermediate 2-pyridyldiazomethane (**67**) obtained by dehydrogenation of pyridine-2-carboxaldehyde hydrazone⁹⁰ (**66**) (Scheme 29).

Scheme 29

2,3-Diazaindolizines have been prepared from 4-aminoquinolinizinium salts also through diazotization followed by 1,5-electrocyclization⁹¹. No analogous synthesis of diazaphosphaindolizines through 1,5-electrocyclization has been developed so far.

Conclusion :

In the present review, an attempt has been made to draw an analogy between the syntheses of phosphorus and the corresponding nonphosphorus heterocycles. Scope of the present review lies in exploring new synthetic routes to phosphaindolizines and related systems by using suitable phosphorus containing reagents.

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